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Exploration of infection Control in Medical Imaging Department during Novel Coronavirus's Period

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ABSTRACT

Novel coronavirus is rampant around the world, causing tens of millions of infections and hundreds of thousands of deaths. Because of its high accuracy, simplicity, convenience and rapidness, medical imaging has become one of the important reference standards for the diagnosis of suspected cases recognized by clinicians. While examining the patients, the imaging department should also strengthen the infection control of medical staff so as to prevent nosocomial infection to the greatest extent. This paper expounds the key points of infection control in medical imaging department from the aspects of personnel configuration, protective equipment management and examination process of medical imaging department, and discusses the key points of infection control from the specific conditions of four departments: CT, ultrasound, magnetic resonance and nuclear medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Novel coronavirus, that is, COVID-19, pathogen is a new type of β -coronavirus, enveloped, particles are round or oval, often pleomorphic, 60~140nm in diameter. Its genetic characteristics are obviously different from those of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, and its transmission routes are respiratory droplets and close contact transmission. (Tan, et.al. 2020) Novel coronavirus is highly contagious and (has a) high fatality rate. As of 18:00 on September 20, 2020, the cumulative number of confirmed cases in the world was 30,967,095 and the death toll reached 960,729. Timely diagnosis of suspected COVID-19 patients, timely isolation treatment to COVID-19 confirmed patients, curbing population flow in epidemic areas, controlling the source of infection, cutting off the route of transmission, and protecting susceptible population are the main measures to effectively control the epidemic of novel coronavirus. COVID-19's gold standard for diagnosis of suspected patients is nucleic acid detection, but due to the influence of many factors, sample collection technology, quality of kit, diversity of disease evolution, and so on, the false negative rate of nucleic acid test is relatively high. As a result, nucleic acid testing can not fully meet the criteria for the diagnosis and discharge of suspected patients. (Zhang, et.al.,2020) Because of its high accuracy, simplicity, convenience and rapidness, medical imaging has

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become one of the important reference standards for diagnosing suspected patients of novel coronavirus approved by clinicians.

The medical imaging department can be divided into four major departments: radiology, magnetic resonance, ultrasonic medicine and nuclear medicine. Some hospitals also bring the interventional department into the category of medical imaging department, but the interventional department is close to the clinical department. The infection control standard should be the same as that of the clinical department, which will not be repeated in this article. Among them, CT and DR in the radiology department play an important role in the diagnosis of COVID-19's suspected patients. In particular, COVID-19's CT images have obvious characteristics, that is, the images show multiple ground-glass opacities, most of which are subpleural and inferior lung fields, and most of them have thickening of pulmonary interstitial septum. Therefore, CT has become an indispensable method for screening and evaluating COVID-19. Although the departments of ultrasound, magnetic resonance and nuclear medicine are not in the first line in COVID-19's diagnosis, because COVID-19 patients have an average incubation period of 14 days, they still have to strictly follow novel coronavirus's infection control requirements. At the same time, some patients have other diseases, and they still need to receive clinical guidance and treatment from clinicians through imaging items other than CT. Therefore, the infection control of novel coronavirus in the imaging department is particularly important.

Research

Overall Layout of Infection Control in Imaging Department

Set Up Novel Coronavirus Infection Management and Control Group of Imaging Department

The director of the imaging department serves as the group leader, the deputy director serves as the deputy group leader, and the director of each department serves as the group member. The team leader coordinates (all quarters concerned, including) the management of protective equipment for medical consumables during the epidemic of COVID-19, the compilation of the infection manual of novel coronavirus in the department, the study of novel coronavirus's knowledge of infection prevention and control, the supervision of the members of the department during the imaging examination of patients, and the psychological counseling and emergency treatment of COVID-19.

The deputy leader should carry out the division of labor, respectively manage the protective equipment of medical consumables, study the knowledge of infection prevention and control of novel coronavirus, supervise doctors and technicians in various departments to conduct standardized image examination and diagnosis, and compile psychological counseling manuals for imaging doctors.

The team members are mainly responsible for the compilation of novel coronavirus protection manual in our department, the standardized training of inspection and diagnosis process during the COVID-19 epidemic situation, and the psychological counseling of staff in our department.

Establishment of Medical Imaging Department Specification for Examination and Approval of the Use of Medical Consumables and Protective Equipment during the COVID-19 Epidemic

During the COVID-19 epidemic, a series of factors, such as the large loss of medical protective equipment, the decline in the production capacity of medical equipment manufacturers due to manpower problems, and the obstruction of logistics due to temporary control, led to a shortage of medical protective equipment. Therefore, it is very important to standardize the use of protective equipment and establish a perfect examination and approval system for the use of medical consumables.

During the epidemic period of COVID-19, the medical supplies of the medical imaging department can be roughly divided into three categories: 1. Protective equipment for doctor, technician and nurse. 2. Disinfection articles on ground, equipment and air. 3. Medical waste, medical waste disinfection and disposal supplies. Among them, the protective equipment are: medical protective masks, overalls, insulating clothing / medical protective clothing, shoe covers, gloves, work caps, positive pressure head covers / comprehensive respiratory protectors, goggles / protective masks, etc. Disinfection articles include chlorine disinfectant, alcohol pads, circulating air disinfectant, ultraviolet lamp and so

on. Medical waste, medical waste disinfection and disposal supplies are: yellow garbage bags, chlorine-containing disinfectants and so on.

In order to facilitate management, these medical consumables can be divided into two categories: disposable consumables and non-disposable consumables. Disposable supplies include: medical protective masks, isolation clothing / medical protective clothing, shoe covers, gloves, work caps, positive pressure head covers / comprehensive respiratory protectors, goggles / protective masks, chlorine disinfectants, alcohol pads and yellow garbage bags. Non-disposable consumables are: overalls, circulating air disinfectant, ultraviolet lamp. (Table 1)

Table 1

Classification of consumables	Personal protective equipment for doctors, technicians, nurses	Ground, equipment, air disinfection articles	Disinfection and disposal supplies of medical waste and medical waste
Disposable	Medical protective masks, isolation clothing / medical protective clothing, shoe covers, gloves, work caps, positive pressure head covers / comprehensive respiratory protectors, goggles / protective masks	Chlorine-containing disinfectants, alcohol cotton tablets	Yellow garbage bags, chlorine-containing disinfectants
Non-disposable	Work clothes	Circulating air disinfectant, ultraviolet lamp	

Disposable consumables need the staff of each department to determine the reported quantity of consumables according to the average number of inspections, and use 20% of the reported quantity of consumables as spare materials in order to avoid a shortage of consumables caused by emergencies. The quantity of consumables required by each department shall be uniformly reported to the deputy team leader in charge of consumables, which shall be confirmed and approved by the team leader and sent to the medical department for examination and allocation. Non-disposable consumables need to be disinfected and maintained regularly by special personnel in each department to ensure the normal and stable operation of the machine.

Significantly, it doesn't mean that it will be better if the medical protective equipment is overabundant and expensive. Wearing too much protective equipment is not easy to be detected when it is contaminated or loosened, and its air permeability is not well. Once soaked by the sweat, the protective performance of it will be weakened. Similarly, it is not necessary to wear N95 masks on all occasions. N95 masks do not prevent droplets from splashing. When conditions permit, window ventilation is easier to achieve purification effect than using air purifier (Li&Wu, 2020).

Use New Media and Internet to Train COVID-19 Related Knowledge

As mass gatherings during this period will greatly increase the risk of infection, the training of medical staff on infection knowledge should be implemented online and can be publicized by using Wechat official accounts, Wechat group chats, and distribution online knowledge manuals. At the same time, after the training, organize COVID-19 infection prevention and control knowledge examination, set up a passing line, and conduct secondary training for those who fail.

Reasonable Arrangement of Working Hours, Regular Psychological Counseling and Intervention

During COVID-19 's period, medical staff in the imaging department had to directly face patients, especially imaging technicians and assistant nurses, facing the risk of direct contact with suspected and confirmed patients,. Coupled with the fact that COVID-19's current route of transmission and

pathogenic mechanism were not clear, some panics were growing and prevailing in the heart of many medical staff. In face of these problems, we should first actively publicize novel coronavirus's mode of infection and protective measures, emphasize to medical staff that protection is in place, and correctly understand that novel coronavirus is preventable and controllable. Secondly, it is necessary to reasonably arrange the working time and rest for half a day every six hours, so as to prevent the medical staff from being overtired. Finally, it is necessary to conduct regular psychological counseling for medical staff and timely investigate the mental health status of medical staff in order to carry out active psychological intervention.

Inspection Process and Control Measures of Radiology Department during COVID-19 Epidemic Situation

The diagnosis of COVID-19 needs to be combined with epidemiological history, clinical manifestations, laboratory tests and imaging findings. Positive nucleic acid detection is the gold standard for the diagnosis of COVID-19, but radiological examination, especially chest CT, can be used as one of the main means for the diagnosis of COVID-19. (Shuai, et.al. 2020) Chest CT examination, as one of the important means for the diagnosis of suspected patients, reexamination of confirmed patients and investigation of epidemic areas, should be the focus of infection control during the epidemic situation of COVID-19 in the imaging department.

CT performance of COVID-19's Chest

The CT findings of COVID-19's chest can be divided into four stages (Table 2): early stage, progressive stage, severe stage and absorption stage (Tan, et.al. 2020). Early COVID-19 chest CT performance: 1. The number of lesions was mainly multiple lesions and a few were single lesions. 2. Focus distribution: mainly distributed in the periphery of the lung, lobar distribution or not according to the lobar distribution, some along the tracheobronchial bundle distribution, multi-lobar distribution, more common in the lower lobe. 3. The shape of the focus: irregular patchy shadow; wedge-shaped or fan-shaped; the long axis is mostly parallel to the pleura; multiple forms can coexist. 4. The boundary of the focus: most of the edges were unclear and some of them were clear. 5. Focus density: mostly ground glass density shadow or mixed ground glass density shadow. 6. Concomitant signs: Halo sign; anti-halo sign; interlobular septal thickening; paving stone sign; slight thickening of bronchial wall and vascular thickening in the lesion. (figure1 A and B).

In the advanced stage, COVID-19's chest CT performance: 1. The number increased: multiple lesions, and the CT findings of new lesions were similar to those of the above-mentioned early lesions. The focus can also increase or decrease. 2. The scope is enlarged: the scope of the lesion is enlarged, which can extend from the subpleura to the hilar region. 3. Morphological changes: the lesions could be fused with consolidation or partially absorbed, and the scope and shape of the lesions changed after fusion, but not according to the shape of the lobes. 4. Density change: consolidation of different size and degree appeared in the focus. Bronchial inflation sign, bronchiectasis, subsegmental atelectasis and a little fibrosis can be seen in consolidation. (figure1 C and D).

Severe stage COVID-19 chest CT performance: 1. The speed of progress: can be rapid in a short period of time, some studies have shown that the obvious progress of the focus within 24-48 hours is more than 50%. 2. The scope of involvement: diffuse distribution, involving the center and periphery of the lungs, the lung fields of both lungs 2 and 3 were involved in time by the lesions, showing the appearance of "white lungs". 3. Focus density: common multiple patchy mixed density foci; diffuse consolidation of both lungs, uneven density, bronchial dilatation sign, bronchiectasis, patchy shadows, ground glass appearance and elevated diaphragmatic surface could be seen in the adjacent non-consolidation area.

Concomitant signs: common thickening of interlobar pleura and bilateral pleura, a small amount of pleural effusion, showing free effusion or local wrapping. (figure1 E)

COVID-19 's chest CT performance during the absorption period: 1. The number of lesions decreased and the scope of lesions contracted . At the same time of absorption of major lesions, new divergence in small lesions can be found in other areas.2. Lesion density: could be absorbed completely, and the density of consolidation area decreased gradually, or cable shadow. 3. Concomitant signs: pleural effusion absorption, pleural thickening reduced or returned to normal. (figure1 F)

Figure 1

Table 2

Stage	Number of lesions	Focus distribution	Focus shape	Focus density
Early stage	Most of the lesions were multiple, and a few were single.	The distribution is mainly in the periphery of the lung, and the distribution of the lobes is not distributed by the lobes.	Irregular patchy shadow; wedge-shaped or fan-shaped; long axis is mostly parallel to the pleura; multiple forms can coexist	Mostly ground glass density shadow or mixed ground glass density shadow
Progressive period	The CT findings of multiple lesions and new lesions were similar to those of the early lesions mentioned above.	The scope of the lesion is enlarged, which can extend from the subpleura to the hilar region.	The lesions can be fused with consolidation or partially absorbed, and the scope and morphology of the lesions will change after fusion.	Consolidation of varying size and degree appeared in the focus.

Severe stage	The lesion progressed more than 50% within 24 hours.	Diffuse distribution, involving the center and periphery of the lung, the lung field above 2 to 3 in both lungs was involved by the lesion.	Common multiple patchy mixed density foci	Interlobar pleura and bilateral pleura are commonly thickened; a small amount of pleural effusion can be seen, showing free effusion or local wrapping.
Absorption period	The number of lesions decreased and the scope of lesions decreased.	The scope of the focus is gradually narrowing.	Suo Tiao Shadow	The ground glass shadow can be completely absorbed, and the density of the compaction zone decreases gradually.

Set Up A Leading Group for Epidemic Infection Control in the Department Of Radiology.

The director of the department shall be the leader of the leading group of epidemic infection control in the radiology department, the deputy chief physician, deputy chief technician and head nurse shall be the deputy head, and the CT doctor, technician, nurse group leader and consumable materials application for warehouse management should be the main members of the leading group (Li, et.al., 2020).

The section director is mainly responsible for the compilation of the novel coronavirus protection manual of the department, the standardized training of the inspection process and diagnosis process during the COVID-19 epidemic, and the management of the deputy team leader.

The deputy chief physician needs to manage the doctor leaders, improve the diagnosis process of COVID-19, and learn the main imaging indications of COVID-19.

Dr. CT team leader needs to lead diagnostic doctors to learn the latest COVID-19 imaging findings and urge doctors to pay attention to safety protection.

The deputy chief technician needs to manage each technician group leader and lead each technician group leader to learn to master the scanning specification and parameter setting of COVID-19 chest CT and the training of disinfection and protection knowledge in each examination room and operation room of CT.

The CT technician team leader needs to lead each technician to learn to master the scanning standard and parameter setting of COVID-19 chest CT and the knowledge of disinfection and protection in each examination room and operation room of CT, and be responsible for the mental health education of each technician at the same time.

The head nurse of CT should instruct technicians and nurses to strictly disinfect and record the rooms of CT, summarize and report the daily consumption of protective equipment and coordinate the allocation of protective materials with the warehouse management of consumable materials.

The warehouse management of consumable materials is mainly responsible for the allocation and replenishment of protective materials.

Standardize the Layout and Planning of the Inspection Area of the Department

As novel coronavirus has the characteristics of aggregated transmission, the principle of three zones and two channels should be strictly followed in the process of patient CT examination, namely,

contaminated area (scanning room, waiting room), semi-polluted area, clean area (changing room, lounge, tea room, etc.), two channels, namely medical staff channel and patient channel, and strictly follow the above requirements (Mei, et.al., 2020)

According to the situation of each hospital, the inspection layout and planning of the department are also different. At present, the layout of CT examination room in radiology department can be divided into two categories: 1. Centralized layout: all the inspection equipment is located in the radiation center and is more centralized. 2. Decentralized layout: some hospital CT inspection equipment are scattered in different wards and different floors, more scattered.

Take the people's Hospital of Henan Province as an example, the people's Hospital of Henan Province centralizes the CT equipment in the basement on the first floor of the outpatient clinic and adopts a centralized layout.

For the decentralized layout, it is necessary to use an independent ct equipment to check COVID-19's suspected patients and fever patients, and a ct to be used for reexamination of COVID-19's confirmed patients. If the number of machines is not enough, a piece of equipment can be checked independently in different periods: if suspected patients are examined in the morning, full sterilization will be carried out at noon, and confirmed patients will be examined in the afternoon.

For the centralized layout, due to the concentration of ct equipment, ordinary patients, suspected patients and diagnosed patients all have to be examined in the same area, so it has become the focus of prevention and control. Take the first affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University as an example, the red area is the polluted area, the yellow area is the semi-polluted area, the green area is the clean area, the waiting area, the technician passage area, the operation room are the semi-polluted area, the diagnosis room is the clean area, and the patient passage and examination room are the contaminated area. All patients need to wear disposable medical masks before entering the waiting area to wait, the operation technician should not contact with the patient as far as possible, the nurse helps the patient to put himself in the right position, and the diagnosis doctor enters the diagnosis room through the doctor's special clean passageway for diagnosis. The diagnosis room is managed in a closed way, and outsiders are not allowed to enter.

Standardize the Procedure of CT Examination and the Reporting Standard of Suspected Patients

During the epidemic of COVID-19, all major hospitals have set up outpatient pre-examination and triage channels to separate fever patients from ordinary patients, and the process of CT examination for different patients should be standardized accordingly.

CT examination procedure for febrile patients (Zhangz&Mao, 2020) first, the fever clinic physician / patient attending physician initiates the process, then informs the CT staff on duty to determine the inspection time and complete personal protection, the logistics department arranges transfer personnel, disinfection personnel, etc., to complete the transfer tool disinfection and personnel in place, and finally the security personnel complete the evacuation and vigilance. Patients need to make one-time isolation sheets before examination, and warning signs need to be posted during the examination to prohibit outsiders from entering. After the examination, the doctor in charge and the diagnostic doctor will read the film immediately. If novel coronavirus is confirmed to enter the infection process of novel coronavirus, if excluded, he will return to the general outpatient clinic or the original ward. After the patient leaves, disinfect the patient channel and the computer room.

Ct examination procedure for ordinary patients (Shuai, et.al. 2020): first, the patient enters the ordinary CT examination channel, and the technician checks the chest CT image immediately after completing the chest CT examination. If the image does not conform to the imaging characteristics of COVID-19, tell the patient to leave. If the highly suspected patient is highly suspected, let the patient stay in place and report to the chief resident of the department for further diagnosis. If the case is not confirmed, tell the patient to leave. If the patient is confirmed, report to the fever clinic for further isolation and investigation. (figure 2)

Figure 2

Protection Grade and Protection Specification for Medical Staff in CT Examination Room

Radiology doctors and nurses take different protective measures according to the patients they come into contact with, and the level of protection can be divided into three levels.

The third level of protection is used for the examination of COVID-19's diagnosed patients. The main protective equipment are isolation clothing / medical protective clothing, shoe covers, gloves, work cap, N95 mask and three layers of latex gloves.

Secondary protection is used for the examination of suspected patients of COVID-19. The main protective equipment are isolation clothing / medical protective clothing, shoe covers, gloves, work caps, medical surgical masks and two layers of latex gloves.

First-class protection is used for general patient examination, the main protective equipment are overalls, latex gloves, medical surgical masks.

In order to minimize the chance of infection and protect health care workers, it is necessary to wear and take off protective equipment (Qin&Li, 2020).

Order of wearing protective equipment: change personal clothing, wear overalls, hand hygiene, wear medical protective mask, wear disposable round hat, wear goggles / protective face screen, wear medical protective clothing, disposable long sleeve boot cover, wear disposable gloves.

Order of removing protective equipment: take off disposable long sleeve boot cover, take off gloves, remove hand hygiene, remove protective clothing for medical use, remove goggles / protective face screen, remove disposable round hat, remove medical protective mask, remove hand hygiene, take off overalls and change personal clothing.

Inspection Process and Control Measures of Ultrasound Department during COVID-19 Epidemic Situation

Although ultrasonic medicine is not the preferred imaging examination for COVID-19's diagnosis, it is still one of the key points of novel coronavirus's infection control because of its large flow, dense patients and crowded examination room.

The configuration of infection control team, planning and layout of departments and disinfection of medical equipment in ultrasound medicine are the same as CT examination, which will not be discussed here. In view of the characteristics of large flow of people and dense patients in the ultrasound department, it is necessary to focus on the process of ultrasonic medical examination and the protection level and standardization of personnel in the department.

Standardize the Inspection Process of COVID-19 during the Epidemic Situation in the Department of Ultrasonic Medicine

Before the ultrasound examination, the hospital will conduct a pre-examination and triage of the outpatient clinic, dividing the patients into three categories: 1. Ordinary patients 2. Febrile patients 3. Suspected and confirmed patients. According to different types of patients, the examination process can be divided into three categories: for ordinary patients, ultrasound doctors use primary protection, and sterilized ultrasound probes can be used in the examination process. The examination of febrile patients requires ultrasound doctors to take secondary protective measures to disinfect the ultrasound examination room. at the same time, the consultation room shall not be used again on the same day, and the protective equipment shall be handled by special personnel. For suspected and confirmed patients, ultrasound doctors need to provide three levels of protection, use disposable ultrasound probes, and fully disinfect all instruments, consulting rooms and patient passages at the end of the examination (Li, 2020). (figure 3)

Figure 3

Standardize the Protection Level of Personnel in Ultrasonic Medicine

The ultrasound department is different from the CT examination room, because of the large flow of people, the protection level should be specified according to the job position.

First-level protection: for triage personnel in ultrasound department and related staff for ordinary ultrasound examination. It is required to wear disposable work cap, medical surgical mask, overalls and so on.

Secondary protection: used for intracavitary, radiography, puncture, interventional ultrasound examination, and related staff for febrile patients. It is required to wear disposable work cap and medical use Section mask, work clothes, isolation clothes, gloves, goggles and so on.

Level III protection: used for ultrasonic examination of suspected or confirmed COVID-19 patients. It is required to wear disposable work cap, medical protective mask (N95), protective clothing, and two layers of gloves, goggles, and rain boots and so on.

Standardize the disinfection process of ultrasonic medicine

The key to the disinfection of ultrasonic medicine lies in the disinfection of ultrasonic probe, which can be divided into three levels according to the contact position of ultrasonic probe.

A probe that comes into contact with intact skin and performs in vitro examinations of the abdomen, small organs, and heart. The method of disinfection is to wipe the coupling agent clean with a paper towel soaked with alcohol, and then wipe the surface of the probe with a disinfection towel.

The second level is contact with mucous membrane, such as transesophageal or vaginal probes or probes that come into contact with pathologically damaged skin. The disinfection method is to wrap the probe with a protective film during the inspection and wipe the probe with gauze soaked in hydrogen peroxide after the inspection is over.

The third level is an ultrasonic probe that is used during the operation when exposed to blood or body fluids and examines the patient in the case of complete disinfection. The method of disinfection is to wrap it with aseptic protective film during inspection.

The probe, using a disposable aseptic coupling agent, soak the probe in 2% peracetic acid solution for 15 minutes after the inspection, and finally wipe it clean with normal saline.

Tandardize the Procedure of Emergency Ultrasound Intervention Examination

Compared with other intervention methods, ultrasonic intervention has many advantages, such as minimally invasive, convenient and efficient, so it is suitable for COVID-19 patients who are in urgent need of suction and drainage. (Zhang, et.al.,2020) it should be noted that before ultrasound intervention, be sure to check the relevant epidemiological history, fever and respiratory symptoms and no suspicious imaging findings of chest CT. Secondary protection was adopted for ordinary patients and tertiary protection was adopted for patients with fever and diagnosed by COVID-19. At the same time, it is necessary to strictly implement the aseptic principle of the puncture equipment, and comprehensively kill the equipment and rooms after operation.

The key points of prevention and control in the Department of Magnetic Resonance and Nuclear Medicine during COVID-19's epidemic situation.

Strictly implement the appointment system of magnetic resonance imaging and nuclear medicine examination, and strictly prevent suspected cases.

The Department of Magnetic Resonance and Nuclear Medicine did not undertake the task of COVID-19's first-line diagnosis and treatment during COVID-19's period, but for ordinary patients, since the incubation period of novel coronavirus can reach 14 days, for patients, we must strictly carry out the procedure of making an appointment for examination and strictly guard against suspected cases.

Before the magnetic resonance and nuclear medical examination, the doctor in charge must carefully inquire and investigate the epidemic history of the patient, and carry out CT examination on the patient to confirm that the patient does not have the typical medical imaging manifestation of COVID-19 before the magnetic resonance and nuclear medical examination can be carried out. For patients with fever, the fever clinic should be diagnosed and treated first, and the infection of novel coronavirus should be excluded before magnetic resonance imaging and nuclear medicine examination can be carried out (Wang, et. al., 2020).

According to the epidemiology and symptoms of the patients, the patients can be divided into four levels: level 1: ordinary patients, local residents, cohabitants and themselves have no history of non-local travel, no experience of collective activities, no symptoms of fever, dry cough and dyspnea. Level 2: potential suspected infection, which means that local residents, themselves and their cohabitants have a 14-day history of traveling in non-epidemic areas and have the experience of group gathering activities, but there are no symptoms such as fever, dry cough, dyspnea and so on. Level 3: medium risk suspected infection. It means that local residents or cohabitants have a history of traveling in the epidemic area within 14 days, have the experience of group gathering activities, but have no symptoms such as fever, dry cough, and dyspnea and so on. Level 4: high-risk suspected infection, refers to the history of travel to the epidemic area within 14 days, the experience of mass gathering activities, fever, dry cough, dyspnea and other suspected symptoms of COVID-19. (Table 3)

Table 3 (Y:yes ;N:no)

Grading	History of out-of-town travel within 14 days		Agglomerat ion activity	Symptoms		
	Non-epidemic area	Epidemic area		Fever	Dry cough	Dyspnea
I	N	N	N	N	N	N
II	Y	N	Y	N	N	N
III	N	Y	Y	N	N	N
IV	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Strictly implement the protection procedures for medical personnel in the departments of magnetic resonance and nuclear medicine according to grades.

According to the classification of patients, the first and second level of protection is used, the third level of protection is used, and the fourth level of protection is adopted.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the epidemic period of COVID-19 in the imaging department, it is necessary to set up a leading group for epidemic management and control, conduct an appointment registration system for inspection in the imaging department, and deploy protective materials at the same time. In different departments, key prevention and control should be carried out in different directions according to the characteristics of different departments: CT is responsible for the differential diagnosis of COVID-19 patients, no matter the examination process, disinfection of medical staff and wearing protective clothing all need to be strictly regulated; ultrasound department has a dense flow of people, to do a good job in the prevention and control of potential infection; magnetic resonance and nuclear medicine departments need to strictly standardize the appointment process.

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